

ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SUSTAINABLE TOURISM PRACTICES

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United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) has defined sustainable tourism as; "Tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities". For successful implementation of sustainable tourism practices it is important to deliver the message to all the stakeholders in a way, that it captures their imagination. In the context of travel and tourism, the memorable travel experiences are all about stories - stories of the local communities and their cultural traditions, stories told by the guides, and stories by the travelers themselves, become part of the travel experiences. In early human history, there was a oral tradition when people used to sit together to hear the experiences of those who have traveled far and wide, witnessed something new or, simply wanted to pass their legacy to their successors. Those who heard the story owned the idea. In the broadcast era, ideas became the exclusive property of their creator. Communication became monologue instead of dialogue. The audience was open and receptive in the oral tradition when stories were dominated. A story engages its listeners at many levels, so when the storyteller makes the point, it sticks, because it evokes both visual image and emotion. In the broadcast era that turns to captive audience. However, again with the advent of social media, now we're getting back into the initial stage where everybody owns an idea. What is different today is we are in an era where stories dominate again. Social media and storytelling are helping to communicate with the audience in a more humane way. It's simply people sharing stories with other people. The technology facilitates and accelerates the process. The paper aims to explore the role of social media in storytelling for sustainable tourism practices, which ultimately leads to sustainability.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing, Storytelling Practices, Sustainable Tourism, Destination Management

The World Commission on Environment and Development, also known as Brundtland Commission, was constituted to pursue the goal of sustainable development, in December 1983. The Brundtland Commission prepared a report "Our Common Future" in October 1987, which defined the term sustainable development as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." This report set the stage for the Earth Summit, held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in 1992. The outcome of this summit was Agenda 21, which was a voluntarily accepted action plan to maintain a synergy between economic growth, ecosystems and a safe & prosperous future. In Agenda 21, travel and tourism were the only industries identified as having the potential to make a positive contribution towards a sustainable planet. In 1995, UNWTO formulated the "Agenda 21 for the Travel & Tourism Industry" towards environmentally sustainable development. It defined sustainable tourism as "one that meets the needs of present tourists and of the host regions while protecting and promoting opportunities for the future".

Storytelling on Social Media

Tourism is all about stories and storytelling. A travel experience, either good or bad evokes a story, and social media, which have created unprecedented platform and virtually unlimited audience for sharing stories, fan this urge of storytelling. Stories are ways of looking a thing and

it brings an idea, which gets shared with everyone, and in turn the recipient also started to own that idea.

To successfully implement an idea it is imperative that each and every stakeholder own the idea. There are four major stakeholders of tourism industry; tourists, people in the business of tourism, host communities and the government. Each of them has different perspective and attitude towards the concept of sustainable tourism practices. The government wanted to implement it, the host communities, who will be and are most affected are silent spectators by and large, and the people in business as well travelers, who are uneasy, unwilling or unaware. However, the advent of social media has provided a unique opportunity to bring all the stakeholders of tourism industry on a common platform. In the travel and tourism context, the positive impact of good storytelling in promoting a destination has already been in practice from quite a sometime now. This "social storytelling" is about shaping social media content into stories that catches the eyeballs, get shared and generate some call to action.

Following are the objectives of the study:

1. To explore the role of storytelling in sustainable tourism

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practices

2. To evaluate the trend of social storytelling in the context of Indian tourism

I. Review of Literature

Eric Miller, the founder of World Storytelling Institute, defined story as a series of events and storytelling as relating a series of events. According to Miller, "we can study how a story is told/performed/presented (presentation analysis) and also, we can study the actual content of the story (content analysis). A distinction can be made between actual storytelling, and presenting a story through other mediums. The difference is that in actual storytelling, the tellers and listeners can give instantaneous and ongoing feedback to each other. However in mediated situations like social media, the level of interactivity in terms of immediacy of feedback remains quite same". Miller further added that "projection, identification, empathy, imitation, and imagination are important processes when it comes to people and stories. People project themselves into story characters. They identify with the characters. They feel empathy with the characters. This occurs through the use of the listener's imagination. The listener may then imitate the character".

Agenda setting, design and implementation constitutes a traditional distinction between key phases in policy-making (Hogwood & Gunn, 1986; Therkelsen & Halkier, 2010) and appear to be useful also in the context of inculcating certain practices through storytelling efforts. As storytelling is studied in the context of sustainable tourism practices, public tourism organizations, local municipalities and regional councils are likely to be central stakeholders in the agenda setting phase. Also private and public tourism stakeholders (e.g. hotels, museums, natural parks, protected areas, tourist attractions, nature tourists guide), local communities and travelers plays a crucial role when the agenda of the storytelling activity is set, as all of them are fundamental players in the process of storytelling.

Stories immerse in people in plots and characters (McCabe & Foster, 2006) and this is of importance since contemporary visitors do not merely encounter the physical space of a destination, they create their own experiential space using their individual motivations and interpretations (Suvantola, 2002). As argued by Chronis (2005), a story performed in interaction with visitors becomes a puzzle with many different pieces that visitors interpret, shape, and try to put together when forming their experiences of the destination since "...service providers do not simply teach history and tourists do not only learn about the past. Rather, through their interaction, marketers and tourists perform history by means of negotiation, narrative completion and embodiment" (Chronis, 2005, p. 400).

Human beings are fundamentally narrative creatures. For them, stories are not only ways of looking at life but looking beyond themselves as well. The noted writer, artist and director Mahmood Farooqui, who specializes in a particular type of story-telling known as Dastangoi says that "the storytellers are the custodian of the history of the community, the narratives of the community, the rituals of the community, as well the community's worldview in larger scenario". Writer Gyan Prakash believes that tradition of storytelling was the basis of epics in India and elsewhere. In his opinion, "the epic bring together whole range of human experiences and emotions, predicament, paradoxes, ironies all in a very accessible and compelling form".

Sustainable Tourism, Eco Tourism and Responsible Tourism

The terms like 'Sustainable Tourism', 'Eco Tourism' and 'Responsible Tourism' are rooted in the concept of sustainable development and intended to benefits local communities and destinations environmentally, culturally and economically. The International Ecotourism Society (TIES) has proposed a revised definition of ecotourism in 2015 as, "responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of the local people and involves interpretation and education" with the specification that education is to staff and guests. The newly included word 'interpretation' is quite significant as it aims to broaden the scope as well acceptance of the concept of sustainable tourism which ultimately contributes to the larger meaning of sustainability.

TIES have proposed following ecotourism principles for those who implement, participate in, and market ecotourism activities:

1. Minimize physical, social, behavioral, and psychological impacts.
2. Build environmental and cultural awareness, and respect.
3. Provide positive experiences for both visitors and hosts.
4. Produce direct financial benefits for conservation.
5. Generate financial benefits for both local people and private industry.
6. Deliver memorable interpretative experiences to visitors that help raise sensitivity to host countries' political, environmental, and social climates.
7. Design, construct and operate low-impact facilities.
8. Recognize the rights and spiritual beliefs of the Indigenous People in your community and work in partnership with them to create empowerment.

II. Research Design & Method

The methodology for this study was qualitative textual analysis, emphasizing the in-depth examination of the content. Manning and Cullum-Swan (1994) divide the analysis of documentary data into the following

categories: “content and narrative analysis”, “structuralism” and “semiotics”. This system views texts as ‘symbolic action’ and assumes the role of words and images in representing, dramatizing and shaping society (Manning and Cullum-Swan, 1994: 465). Since the aim of this paper is to explore the role of storytelling in sustainable tourism practices through social media, therefore in-depth analysis of video content and the related posts on social media websites of Ten Indian States, based on their ranking of foreign tourists’ arrival in India in 2013-14 were observed.

The study has been limited to Facebook and YouTube, as it is observed that most of the tourism websites in India have their active presence on mainly these two social media platforms.

III. Results & Discussion

In the travel industry, stories can be divided into two major categories; stories told by businesses i.e. brand story and stories told by travelers i.e. traveler story.

Brand Story v/s Traveler Story

A traveler story is driven by experience and contains most of the elements of good storytelling: a fascinating lead, a premise that includes apprehension, excitement, motivation, insight and a dose of reality. Travel storytelling is related to the destination marketing. The travel story shared on social media is short, interactive and mostly contains visual elements. In this context, the actual challenge is to maintain the regular supply of fresh, engaging and brand relevant stories to the target audience of different social media platforms. Once a story gets posted by brand it enters into user generated content domain. Now it is up to the user to like, comment or share the content.

For organization or businesses, storytelling starts with their brand story which consistently highlights their prime value propositions. Brand stories answer all the probable questions that a traveler or potential traveler may ask. Questions like why should I choose you? Where I suppose to go? What should I expect there? How will I feel? A detailed study has been conducted by analyzing the available content of the “tourism websites”, and their official “Facebook Page” and “YouTube Page” of Ten Indian States. Please refer Table 1.

Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra, the two front runners in receiving foreign tourists, have no visual promotional content on their YouTube page. While the West Bengal, Karnataka and Haryana, didn’t even have official YouTube page. National Capital Delhi though has an official page on YouTube, but do not have any promotional advertising campaign to showcase. Rest four Rajasthan, Bihar, Kerala and Uttar Pradesh have visual stories of their states on YouTube. The most incredible among them is the stories of Rajasthan Tourism, which was launched in January 2016.

In the advertisement sphere the story is as important as the product. Rajasthan has always been a great product in terms of tourism success, but the challenge for Piyush Pandey and team Ogilvy & Mather, who handles this campaign was to give a complete makeover to the story of the Rajasthan.

When one thinks of Rajasthan, desert, camel, massive forts, folk music, colorful clothes come to mind. Vasundhara Raje, the Chief Minister of Rajasthan, wanted to add more value to this perception of Rajasthan. The challenge was to attract the youth to a different Rajasthan, a destination for adventure seekers and explorers, and most importantly to change the perception about the Rajasthan. In Vasundhara Raje views, “Rajasthan has not really taken advantage of its ‘stories’. Rajasthan is not just about the desert and the Palaces. It is much, much more. Every nook of Rajasthan has a story, and that story needs to be told in a glitzy way!”

The brief was beautifully narrated in a simple idea, “beauty lies in the eyes of the beholder”, which in turn executed in advertisements as, “Rajasthan looks different through the eyes of different travelers”. Through the eyes of Huan, it becomes Huansthan. Through the eyes of Jane, it becomes Janesthan. It is not about Rajasthan, it is about visitor that how they want to perceive it. This is also reflecting in Rajasthan tourism ad tagline, “Come to Rajasthan – Jaane Kya Dikh Jaaye!” Please refer Figure 1.

It is imperative from the content of Rajasthan tourism campaign that they are designed in a way to not only cater broadcast audience rather audience on social media too. The new website, new Facebook page and revamped of YouTube page has been designed along with the TV & Print campaign. “Kahin chhut na jaaye Chhath”, video is one such effort that connects the Diaspora to its roots. This three minute video on ‘Chhath Puja’ by the Bihar Tourism has become a rage in the web world by getting more than 1,11,000 views till date. The video shows a young man working at his office in Mumbai, when he gets a call from his mother asking him to come home for Chhath, but unwillingly he has to say no as he is loaded with work. Thereafter, a SMS of his younger sister compelled him to walk down to the memory lane, while the Chhath song sung by famous singer Sharda Sinha plays in the background. At the end of the video, he is finally shown joining his mother and sister at the early morning arghya with the Sun God witnessing the union.

Chhath Puja is a major festival celebrated in Bihar. The story in this video not only connects to the Diaspora of the Bihar but also pitch strongly for the beautiful tradition of worshipping Sun God for supporting life on earth and ensuring prosperity and happiness in life. This video seems to strike all the right chords at it is evident in the comment section of the YouTube link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_e-hBFZdL3I. Most of the people were showing

the desire to join the festival, and praise was coming from those too who doesn't even belong to the state. Please refer Figure 2.

The videos shared on YouTube are mostly "brand story", a means of visual storytelling. The videos are trusted most as they can't be exaggerated like text or photoshopped like images. Understanding the impact of visual storytelling in changing the perception of tourists, Kerala Tourism as well Uttar Pradesh Tourism too has their brand stories on their official YouTube channel. However, the statistics of these official YouTube channel's of Bihar, Kerala, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh tells a story in itself. When the brand story is only talking about their own offerings the number of subscribers is low, but when there is a human way of storytelling, when the brand story is taking the backseat and giving the way to traveler story, the number of hits, share, subscription and comments are on higher side. The statistics of Bihar Tourism "Kahin chhut na jaye Chhath" video was not made available on YouTube, but it has 1984 likes and 186 comments, which is by far the maximum in comparison to other three videos taken. Please refer Table 2.

After brand story which is told by the businesses, traveler story are the next category of storytelling on social media. Daniel Edward Craig, who works in the area of online reputation management and social media strategy for travel industry; writes in his blog 'ReKnown' that, A traveler story can be as simple as "I was here" or "I like this place" or "I recommend it". In his opinion, these stories can be considered as more potent first because they are coming from unbiased source and secondly unlike marketers, storytellers are not going to get anything out of the positive action taken by other visitors. Please refer Table 3.

The "Likes" and "Talking About" numbers on Facebook

"Likes" Simply means someone at some point, clicked the "like" button once. It could be either directly on a Facebook page or somewhere else as well. "Talking About" is the actual number of people who are 'engaged' and interacting with that Facebook Page. These people actually come back to the page after liking the page. This includes activities such as comments, likes to a post, shares, etc by visitors to the page. "Talking about" should be ideally 10% if total page like is less than 100,000 and it should be 5% total likes for a page is more than 100,000.

Why people share

The New York Times customer insight group published a study to understand the psychology of sharing on social media. The study covered few important drive behind sharing like; primary motivation for sharing, sharing personas, cycle of sharing, impact of sharing on information

management etc. among others. There is nothing new in sharing; people are always sharing since the beginning of humanity. It is just that with the social media at disposal we share more. We share more content – from more sources – with more people – more often – more quickly. From the NYT study the key fact that came out is; sharing is all about relationship. People share:

1. To bring valuable and entertaining content to others to enrich their lives
2. To define themselves to others
3. To grow and nourish relationship
4. To let others know about things they care

IV. Conclusion

According to a research by "University of Pennsylvania", emotive contents get shared most on social media. And storytelling is an effective way to convey this emotive content. The human emotions both positive and negative like wonder, witty, touching, enlightening, exciting, shocking, freighting, and anger, work in favor of getting content shared. Statistics from 'Pinterest' and 'Instagram' shows that the images that resonate with viewers and get shared are images that have an emotive element, and tell a story. We are in the midst of a connected consumer revolution happening in a post broadcast-world. The consumer decides and control that what they will view? What they will share? And how they will do it? A major shift can be witnessed which mark the relationship between consumers and marketers. One of the best ways to take the message to the target audience is by combining the power of storytelling with social media. However it is important to understand here that all these technologies are merely facilitating and accelerating the process and this can't undermine the power of compelling storytelling, where people are simply sharing stories with others to share the idea, which eventually own by all.

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Table 1: Top 10 Indian State based on their ranking of foreign tourist arrival in 2013-14

S.No.	State	Tourism Website	Facebook Page	YouTube Page
1	Tamil Nadu	http://www.tamilnadutourism.org/	https://web.facebook.com/tnttdc/?ref=sgm	https://www.youtube.com/user/thetamilnadutourism One video in Tamil
2	Maharashtra	http://www.maharashtratourism.gov.in/	https://web.facebook.com/MaharashtraTourismDevelopmentCorporationLtd/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC85msVxCQkwgkN15VkNq2hA No Content
3	Uttar Pradesh	http://uptourism.gov.in/	https://web.facebook.com/UttarPradeshTourism?cd=MQA0ADcA	https://www.youtube.com/user/uptourismgov?app=desktop&cd=MQA0ADkA
4	Delhi	http://www.delhitourism.gov.in/delhitourism/index.jsp	https://web.facebook.com/delhitourism/?v=wall&ref=ts	https://www.youtube.com/user/DTTDC1
5	Rajasthan	http://tourism.rajasthan.gov.in/	https://web.facebook.com/rajasthan tourism	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCFibxqea7JmKpUWwStpl8bA
6	West Bengal	http://www.wbtourism.gov.in/ http://www.westbengaltourism.gov.in/ http://www.wbtfdc.gov.in/	https://web.facebook.com/tourismwb/	No official YouTube Page.
7	Kerala	https://www.keralatourism.org/	https://www.facebook.com/keralatourismofficial	https://www.youtube.com/user/keralatourism
8	Bihar	http://bstdc.bih.nic.in/ http://www.bihartourism.gov.in/	https://web.facebook.com/13bihar.tourism https://web.facebook.com/www.bihartourism.gov.in	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSJdD5U86NPR04xMnC9NrIw https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCKjIKHTFPbmYJ7CY6-gEBkg
9	Karnataka	http://www.karnatakaholidays.net/	https://web.facebook.com/Karnataka-Tourism-Fan-page-126437450701472/	No official YouTube Page
10	Haryana	http://haryanatourism.gov.in/	No official Facebook Page	No official YouTube Page

Table 2: Analysis of highest viewed advertisement of YouTube channel of four states (as of 30/01/2016)

Official YouTube Page	A single advertisement with maximum number of			
	Views	Time Watched	Subscriptions Driven	Shares
Bihar	111373	NA	NA	NA
Rajasthan	115310	56 days	98	401
Kerala	55192	92 days	57	1232
Uttar Pradesh	619	19 hours	4	10

Table 3: Analysis of Facebook Page of 10 states based on their ranking of foreign tourist arrival in 2013-14 (as of 30/01/2016)

States	Likes	Visits	People talking about this	Ratings	Reviews
Tamil Nadu	4803	15	46	4.3	15
Maharashtra	100790	291	739	4.5	173
Uttar Pradesh	43007	511	3086	4.6	153
Delhi	7743	253	37	3.9	33
Rajasthan	4902	N.A.	94	N.A.	N.A.
West Bengal	557685	355	8342	4.4	551
Kerala	1182533	N.A.	17645	N.A.	N.A.
Bihar	3602	N.A.	10	N.A.	N.A.
Karnataka	167105	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Haryana	No official Facebook page				

Figure 1: Rajasthan Tourism Logo

Figure 2: YouTube page grab of the comment section of the “Chhath Puja” film

